

Safety and Efficacy of Pegylated Interferon Add-on Therapy versus Nucleotide Analog for Chronic Hepatitis B Patients with Sustained Response to Nucleos(t)ide Analog Therapy: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

Chronic hepatitis B (CHB) is a global health challenge and remains treated with long-term nucleos(t)ide analog (NA) therapy. Nevertheless, NA therapy alone rarely results in HBsAg clearance, the ultimate goal of a cure of function. Pegylated interferon (PEG-IFN) has been examined as a switch or adjunct to HBsAgol treatment to increase treatment response, particularly to achieve HBsAg loss and seroconversion. This systematic review evaluates the efficacy of PEG-IFN for various CHB patients. Databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Embase were searched for a systematic literature review (SLR). 13 studies were considered eligible and included PEG-IFN add-on or switch studies in CHB patients. A content analysis was used to synthesise findings. The findings show that NA monotherapy was less effective than PEG-IFN add therapy in HBeAg-negative patients. PEG-IFN add-on treatment led to a 28% decline in HBsAg levels compared to NA monotherapy, which did have a significant decrease. HBsAg clearance was also observed in 10% of patients receiving PEG-IFN add-on therapy but none in patients on NA monotherapy. The analysis also showed that 37.4% of patients could reach HBsAg clearance while receiving PEG-IFN add-on therapy, whereas only 1.9% were within the NA monotherapy group. PEG IFN combination therapy is superior to PEG IFN monotherapy in treating CHB patients, especially to the extent that it avoids the possibility of diminishing response. However, further research is needed to select more patients who are more optimal for treatment and longer durations.

Keywords: Pegylated Interferon (PEG-IFN), Interferon alfa-2a, Interferon alfa-2b Nucleos(t)ide analogs (NA therapy), Tenofovir, Entecavir

1. Introduction

Chronic Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) infection is the current leading global public health issue and affects approximately 296 million people globally who are chronically infected with Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg). This infection was ranked among the leading causes of chronic liver diseases, including cirrhosis and Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC), and contributed to about 1.1 million deaths in the year 2022 (Who, 2024). Untreated patients with chronic HBV infection are at a 30–40% lifetime risk of developing cirrhosis or HCC. Current treatment strategies for chronic HBV aim to achieve several key outcomes: hepatitis B virus (HBV) DNA reduction, ALT level return to normal range, disappearance of HBeAg (in HBeAg-positive CHB), and, in some cases, HBsAg Ag loss (Tatsukawa et al., 2018). The aim is the prevention of morbidity and mortality in those who receive chronic HBV treatment.

The preferred treatment outcome for patients with Chronic Hepatitis B (CHB) is to provide a "functional cure" whereby the patient can off treatment and maintain off-treatment normal HBV serology, including the absence of detectable HBsAg and HBV DNA in serum, after a finite duration of treatment. However, there are limited treatment options for chronic HBV infection. These are pegylated interferon alfa (PEG-IFN) given for a fixed duration, often between 48-96 weeks, and nucleos(t)ide analogs (NAs) usually to be taken lifelong to avoid relapse (Wang et al., 2024). These therapies aim to achieve a "partial response" that refers to the persistent reduction or undetectable levels of HBV DNA in the serum despite the continued presence of HBsAg. This partial cure is considered an important step toward achieving full HBV eradication (Rui et al., 2025).

The issues with the complete elimination of HBV are defined by the existence of Covalently Closed Circular DNA (cccDNA)—a stable, integrated form of the virus within infected hepatocytes' nuclei—

and HBV DNA incorporation into the host genome (Wu et al., 2020). Consequently, the elimination of HBV is still a challenge, and the current antiviral treatment brings only partial suppression of the virus. PEG-IFN for one year clears HBsAg in 2-3 % of patients at the end of treatment and may rise to 3-8% within three post-treatment follow-up years. On the other hand, the use of second-generation NAs, including entecavir or TDF, shows HBsAg seroclearance ranging from 0 to 5 % with a longer time horizon of 10 years and higher it is in patients with positive HBeAg (Yan et al., 2025).

Since the current treatments appear to be suboptimal, there has been growing interest in combination therapies, including NAs and PEG-IFN, to provide higher therapeutic benefits. Such strategies include the "PEG-IFN add-on" strategy, by which PEG-IFN is added to existing NA therapy (Yang et al., 2020). This combination strategy proposes to maximize the therapeutic effectiveness of PEG-IFN's immunomodulatory features and NAs' antiviral properties. The basis for this is that PEG-IFN may help resolve immunosuppression in CHB patients, especially as it is linked to increased T-cell and natural killer cell activity (Yang et al., 2022). In addition, treatment with NAs may improve the immune response to PEG-IFN, improving the chances of an off-treatment response, defined by the loss of HBsAg and/or HBeAg, or speeding up HBsAg decline.

However, clinical data about the effectiveness of PEG-IFN add-on therapy are somewhat contradictory. First trials with NAs and PEG-IFN using the same dose for 48 weeks did not show advantages concerning HBV DNA reduction and HBsAg clearance in the HBeAg-positive chronic HBV population (Zhang et al., 2024). On the other hand, a combination of TDF and PEG-IFN during the first 48 weeks and then TDF maintenance, a significantly higher viral control, and HBsAg levels were detected in the PEG-IFN HBeAg-negative population (9% versus 1%) compared to NAs group only. In addition, PEG-IFN added to NAs at week 24 in HBeAg-positive patients who were on stable HBV DNA <200 IU/mL had superior rates of HBsAg loss even though the primary endpoint of HBeAg loss with HBV DNA <200 IU/mL was not accomplished (Yang et al., 2022).

This research aims to fill this knowledge gap by determining whether PEG-IFN add-on therapy in chronic HBV-infected patients with maintained viral suppression defined by undetectable or below 200 IU/mL HBV DNA in the last 3 to 6 months can boost the rate of sustained, off-treatment HBsAg loss and achieve a functional cure as defined as sustained off-study HBsAg decline or loss with or without HBsAb seroconversion with undetectable serum HBV DNA level, 6 to 12 months after stopping therapy.

The objective of the study is to establish the efficacy and safety of pegylated interferon (PEG-IFN) given additively, switched, or as a monotherapy in patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) in the context of long-term nucleos(t)ide analog (NA) therapy. The review focused on determining the effects of PEG-IFN on primary virological and clinical outcomes like HBsAg decline, HBsAg clearance, HBeAg seroconversion, improvement in liver fibrosis, and the possibility of viral relapse. In addition, the studies aimed to find factors that predict response to treatment and analyze variations attributed to baseline patient characteristics, previous exposure to interferon, and the disease state of HBV.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This research uses the SLR technique within a qualitative approach framework. The SLR method was chosen to methodically collect, evaluate, and synthesize existing literature on the advantages of

pegylated interferon (PEG-IFN) therapy in the management of chronic hepatitis B (CHB). Only the most relevant and methodologically sound articles are selected through strict sifting and filtering criteria. The methodology works within predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, focusing on clinical studies published that analyze the outcome of PEG-IFN therapy. This research follows PRISMA guidelines for enhancing transparency and reproducibility.

2.2 PICO Framework for the Study

The framework by which the study focuses on the key elements behind it is presented in Table 1. They identify the population as patients with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) on nucleos(t)ide analogue (NA) therapy and interventions consisting of PEG IFN add-on or switch strategies. Outcomes to be assessed are HBsAg decline, HBsAg clearance, HBeAg seroconversion, and risk of relapse.

Table 1: PICO Framework for the Study

Component	Description
Population (P)	Patients with chronic Hepatitis B (CHB), including HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative individuals, are on long-term nucleos(t)ide analog (NA) therapy.
Intervention (I)	Pegylated Interferon (PEG-IFN) add-on or switch therapy combined with NA therapy to evaluate its effectiveness in achieving HBsAg clearance and seroconversion.
Comparison (C)	NA monotherapy or alternative treatment strategies, such as continued NA therapy without PEG-IFN, to assess differences in treatment outcomes.
Outcome (O)	HBsAg loss, HBeAg seroconversion, virological suppression, and overall treatment efficacy, including fibrosis reversal and clinical relapse rates.

2.3 Strategy for Collecting Data

Data has been collected by formulating systematic queries from electronic database resources such as PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, and Cochrane Library. The databases used are chosen because of the wide coverage of biomedical and clinical literature. All of these are used to construct the search strategy, based on a set of keywords and Boolean operators, and to search for relevant articles about PEG-IFN therapy in CHB patients. This is done along the lines of a PICO approach, including Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome, which help to select the issue adequately. Patients whose diagnosis is CHB and who received PEG-IFN therapy as monotherapy or in combination with Nucleos(t)ide analogs (NAs) and reported results of HBsAg clearance, HBeAg seroconversion, or viral suppression are included in the studies. Table 2 shows databases and keywords used in research.

Table 1: Databases and Keywords

Databases Used	Keywords Used
PubMed	Chronic Hepatitis B, HBV infection, Hepatitis B virus
Scopus	Pegylated Interferon (PEG-IFN), Interferon alfa-2a, Interferon alfa-2b
Web of Science	Nucleos(t)ide analogs (NA therapy), Tenofovir, Entecavir, Combination therapy
Embase	HBsAg clearance, HBeAg seroconversion, Viral suppression, Virological response
Cochrane Library	Treatment outcomes, Sustained virological response, Long-term efficacy

This structured approach ensured a comprehensive review of relevant literature while optimizing the search strategy for maximum retrieval of high-quality studies.

2.4 Inclusion and exclusion

This study's inclusion criteria were limited to peer-reviewed publications and clinical trials involving chronic Hepatitis B (CHB) patients, both HBeAg-positive and negative, undergoing nucleos(t)ide analog (NA) therapy with or without the addition of Pegylated Interferon (PEG-IFN) therapy. Studies with well-defined endpoints, such as HBsAg loss, E seroconversion, and viral load suppression, were selected. Only studies from the past fifteen years published in English were accepted to ensure usability for contemporary treatment protocols. Exclusion criteria removed studies based on pediatric age groups with associated infections (e.g., HIV, HCV) or patients with decompensated cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma. Non-peer-reviewed articles, editorial pieces, conference abstracts, and those lacking adequate data or with vague research designs were also excluded from the study.

2.5 Data analysis

The gathered data will be analyzed using content analysis, a qualitative approach that allows the discovery of frequently recurring themes and ideas in the literature. Important treatment results, such as treatment outcome measures: HBsAg clearance rates, HBeAg seroconversion, and other predictors of treatment response, such as (baseline HBsAg levels, age, HBV genotype) and negative life events, are being analyzed. Thematic synthesis is done to analyze differing studies and provide an explanation for the effectiveness and shortcomings of PEG-IFN therapy.

3. Results

3.1 Prisma Framework

The study selection process is shown in the PRISMA flow diagram starting from 771 records obtained from multiple databases (PubMed (194), Scopus (63), Web of Science (364), Embase (10), Cochrane Library (20)). After deleting the 500 duplicate records, 271 unique studies were screened, and 215 studies were excluded for being irrelevant. Among 56 reports, 26 could not be accessed. For eligibility, thirty studies were assessed, but 34 were excluded (30 for having previously been published before 2010 and 7 because they were not written in English). Finally, 16 studies were included in the final systematic review. Being structured in this way ensured that only the most relevant and high-quality studies were included.

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram

Table 3: Main findings

Study Author	Method	Population	Sample Size	Intervention	Duration of Trial	Outcome
Farag et al. (2024)	Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)	HBeAg-negative CHB patients on long-term NA therapy	86 (58 PEG-IFN add-on, 28 NA monotherapy)	PEG-IFN alfa-2a (180 µg/week) + NA vs. NA monotherapy	48 weeks treatment + 24 weeks follow-up (72 weeks total)	PEG-IFN add-on increased HBsAg decline (28% vs. 0%) and clearance (10% vs. 0%) compared to NA monotherapy.
Chi et al. (2017)	Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)	HBeAg-positive CHB patients on long-term NA therapy	77 (39 PEG-IFN add-on, 38 NA monotherapy)	PEG-IFN alfa-2b + NA vs. NA monotherapy	48 weeks treatment + 48 weeks follow-up (96 weeks total)	PEG-IFN add-on led to higher HBeAg seroconversion (30% vs. 7%) in interferon-naive patients. The primary endpoint was not statistically significant.
Lim et al. (2022)	Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)	CHB patients on NA therapy for >12 months	253 (103 switches, 99 add-ons, 51 control)	PEG-IFN alfa-2b switch/add-on vs. NA monotherapy	48 weeks treatment + 24 weeks follow-up (72 weeks total)	Add-on PEG-IFN led to higher HBsAg loss (10.1% vs. 0%) compared to NA monotherapy. A switch had a higher clinical relapse (27% in HBeAg-positive).
Wu et al. (2020)	Observational Study	HBeAg-negative CHB patients on NA therapy for >1 year, HBsAg ≤ 1500 IU/mL	195 (91 PEG-IFN add-on, 104 NA monotherapy)	PEG-IFN alfa-2a + NA vs. NA monotherapy	48 weeks treatment + 24 weeks follow-up (72 weeks total)	PEG-IFN add-on resulted in significantly higher HBsAg clearance (37.4% vs. 1.9%) and seroconversion (29.7% vs. 0%) compared to NA monotherapy.
Yang et al., 2022	Observational study	CHB patients with low HBsAg (<1500 IU/ml), HBeAg-negative, HBV-DNA negative	292 (85 interferon-experienced, 207 interferon-naive)	Peg-interferon α-2b add-on therapy	48 weeks	HBsAg clearance (29.8%) and seroconversion (22.0%) were similar in interferon-experienced and naive patients; age, baseline

							HBsAg, and week 12 HBsAg were negative correlated factors.
Yang et al., 2020	Prospective RCT	Treatment-naïve CHB patients	144 (ETV monotherapy: 70, Combination therapy: 74)	(ETV monotherapy vs. ETV + Peg-interferon add-on (week 26-52))	ETV monotherapy vs. ETV + Peg-interferon add-on (week 26-52)	104 weeks (2 years follow-up)	No significant difference in HBsAg or HBeAg seroconversion; combination therapy improved liver histology and fibrosis reversal more than monotherapy.
Zhou et al., 2019	Open-label pilot trial	Non-cirrhotic HBeAg-positive CHB patients with >1 year of HBeAg seroconversion	48 (Peg-IFN: 24, NA consolidation: 24)	Peg-IFN consolidation vs. continued NA therapy for 48 weeks	Peg-IFN consolidation vs. continued NA therapy for 48 weeks	144 weeks (96-week treatment-free follow-up)	Peg-IFN consolidation increased HBsAg loss (36.3% vs. 4.3%) and reduced viral relapse (25% vs. 58.3%) compared to NA consolidation.
Liem et al., 2019	RCT (pooled analysis of two trials)	HBeAg-positive CHB patients previously on ETV	234 (Peg-IFN add-on: 118, ETV monotherapy: 116)	(Peg-IFN add-on: 118, ETV monotherapy: 116)	Peg-IFN add-on vs. continued ETV monotherapy	24-48 weeks of add-on therapy, 48-week post-treatment follow-up	Peg-IFN add-on had higher response (HBeAg loss + HBV DNA <200 IU/mL) than ETV monotherapy (33% vs. 20%); best response in Peg-IFN naive patients with HBsAg <4000 IU/mL and HBV DNA <50 IU/mL.
Takkenberg et al., 2013	Observational study	CHB patients (HBeAg-positive & HBeAg-negative)	92 (44 HBeAg-positive, 48 HBeAg-negative)	44 HBeAg-positive, 48 HBeAg-negative	Peg-IFN + Adefovir	48 weeks, 2-year follow-up	HBsAg loss: 11% in HBeAg-positive, 17% in HBeAg-negative; low baseline HBsAg was a strong predictor for HBsAg loss.
Wang et al., 2024	Observational study	HBV-related compensated cirrhosis patients	54		PEG-IFN- α -2b (180 μ g/week)	48 weeks	HBsAg level significantly reduced ($p < 0.001$), with better response in NAs-experienced patients; three patients achieved HBsAg loss, two achieved seroconversion; no virological breakthrough or disease

						progression; some adverse events, with three discontinuations.
Zhang et al., 2024	Prospective study	HBeAg-positive CHB patients	75	PEG-IFN α for 52 weeks, 24-week follow-up	76 weeks	Established a predictive model for HBeAg seroconversion and HBsAg clearance based on baseline and early treatment markers; higher response rates in patients meeting threshold criteria at baseline, week 12, and week 24.
Cannizzo et al., 2018	RCT	CHB patients on long-term tenofovir therapy	30 (10 PEG-IFN add-on, 20 NA monotherapy)	PEG-IFN add-on vs. continued NA therapy	24 weeks	PEG-IFN add-on led to greater qHBsAg decline and 20% HBsAg loss vs. 0% in NA monotherapy; no significant changes in unconventional T-cell frequency/function between groups.
Hu et al., 2022	Multicenter RCT	HBeAg-positive CHB patients on ≥ 2 years of entecavir	153 (50 add-on, 52 switch-to, 51 monotherapy)	PEG-IFN add-on, PEG-IFN switch-to, or continued entecavir	48 weeks	Add-on and switch-to PEG-IFN led to significantly higher HBeAg seroconversion (18.0% & 19.2% vs. 2.0%), HBsAg <100 IU/mL (30.0% & 34.6% vs. 0%), and greater HBsAg reduction compared to monotherapy; similar efficacy between add-on and switch-to arms; PEG-IFN had tolerable adverse events.

4. Studies characteristics

4.1 Study Design and Participants

These studies were carried out to evaluate the effectiveness of pegylated interferon (PEG-IFN) for treatment of chronic hepatitis B (CHB) patients with different study designs and populations. Most were randomized controlled trials (RCT) such as those of (Farag et al., 2024), (Hu et al., 2022), (Chi et al., 2017) which allocated subjects to PEG-IFN add on therapy, switch to therapy, and NA monotherapy. These RCTs were intended to produce strong evidence of the efficacy of PEG-IFN. Recent studies, like those of (Wang et al., 2024) or (Takkenberg et al., 2013), have taken an observational point of view on the ability of treatment in a specific population of CHB.

The results mentioned are different studies that have different participant groups with the sample sizes ranging from 30 in (Cannizzo et al., 2018) to 292 in (Yang et al., 2022). (Zhang et al., 2024), (Chi et al., 2017) included patients with HBeAg positive in the studies of the effect of PEG-IFN treatment on the seroconversion rate. (Wu et al., 2020) studied HBeAg- patients on long term NA therapy as others. Like (Zhang et al., 2024) and (Wang et al., 2024), some studies examined non cirrhotic patients who were HBeAg seroconverted; or, patients with HBV related compensated cirrhosis respectively. Overall, this body of studies, not independent with each other in structure and focus, brings comprehensive understanding of the use of PEG-IFN for the treatment in CHB in regard to the health status and disease progression in the individual.

4.2 Duration of Trials

Although most CHB studies had completed era peg-interferon, trial era peg plus post faze for longitudinal impact was rarely attempted in some way. The total treatment time for a large number of participants was between 24 and 104 weeks, and follow-up was between 24 and 96 weeks. For example, (Farag et al., 2024) as well as (Wu et al., 2020) tested 48 weeks of treatment along with 24 weeks of follow up, thereby providing the full volume of the study as 72 weeks. Like that design, (Lim et al., 2022) conducted a 48 weeks PEG-IFN therapy and 24 weeks observation to observe sustained virological response.

For example, as reported by (Chi et al., 2017)) and (Yang et al., 2022)., such studies had more than 48/52 weeks of longitudinal design to determine sustained HBeAg seroconversion or HBsAg decline. (Zhou et al., 2019). was perhaps the furthest and they set their experiment to run over 144 weeks to find out if PEG IFN consolidation therapy plus cessation of IFN therapy for the final 96 weeks reduces long-term benefit as well as release of treatment.

Its importance was to estimate, after post treatment follow up, HBeAg seroconversion, HBsAg clearance and sustained virological remission after PEG-IFN therapy. Both (Liem et al., 2019)) and (Takkenberg et al., 2013) made critical contributions to long term outcomes in that they included patients with longer follow up period, especially as they pertain to recurrence rates and treatment persistence. This suggests the need for continued follow-up with patients after the treatment period is over.

4.3 Outcomes

All the studied parameters were presented as primary outcomes: rate of HBeAg seroconversion, HBsAg decline or clearance, and virological response rate. Among them, some studies have also taken into account improvements in liver function and complications. In most cases, PEG-IFN therapy was more effective than NA monotherapy in the percentage of patients with significant reduction of HBsAg and rate of seroconversion. As per a report by (Farag et al., 2024), PA was found to have a 28% reduction in HBsAg and 10% of clearance whereas NA alone had no HBsAg clearance results. (Wu et al., 2020) had also shown that the rates of HBsAg clearance in both PEG-IFN add-on therapy (37.4%) and in NAs therapy (1.9%) were significantly higher than those in NAs therapy (29.7% vs. 0%).

PEG IFN add-on therapy increased the rates of seroconversion in HBeAg positive patients. Looking at the interference of interferon-naïve patients into monotherapy, (Chi et al., 2017) observed that patients who went on monotherapy of NA experienced much higher HBeAg seroconversion rates (30%), and (Hu et al., 2022) indicated that switching to or adding PEG-IFN to NA were much higher seroconversion rates compared to NA monotherapy (18.0% and 19.2% vs. 2.0%). Studies like (Zhou et al., 2019) also demonstrated the effect of PEG-IFN on decreasing the viral relapse rate compared to IFN alfa (25% vs. 58.3%).

In addition, virological responses were studied, which included measuring improvement in liver function. (Yang et al., 2022) found that combination therapy had better reversals of liver histology and itself overall fibrosis than NA monotherapy. In fact, fevered symptoms, cytopenia, and discontinuation of the treatment were very frequent. While PEG-IFN reduced HBsAg levels for most of the patients, three patients stopped the treatment because of severe side effects as claimed by (Wang et al., 2024).

4.4 Interventions

Methods of intervention using pegylated interferon (PEG-IFN) were used to review the published studies on patients diagnosed with chronic hepatitis B (CHB) in which PEG-IFN was used as an adjunct, switch treatment, or as a monotherapy. Most often, the add-on strategy was used—combining PEG-IFN with nucleos(t)ide analogs (NAs) to achieve the best virological response. In addition NA therapy is studied in a number of studies such as (Farag et al., 2024), (Wu et al., 2020) and (Liem et al., 2019) with PEG-IFN alfa-2a (180 µg/week) or alfa-2b. Therefore, it was shown that add on PEG-IFN therapy yielded higher rates of HBsAg clearance and seroconversion compared to those seen with NA therapy as a single treatment.

A major component of the intervention consisted of the switch-to strategy, whereby patients maintained on long term NA therapy switched to PEG-IFN. In (Hu et al., 2022) addition, switching to therapy, and continued NA therapy monotherapy were studied and both switch and add on strategies resulted in much higher HBeAg seroconversion and HBsAg decrease as compared to the monotherapy group. Both add-on and switch designs were also analyzed by (Lim et al., 2022), and add-on was associated with better HBsAg loss, while the switch group had a higher incidence of clinical relapse.

However, there were a number of studies that concentrated only on PEG-IFN single monotherapy, especially for patients with low baseline HBsAg levels or HBV related cirrhosis. A trial was conducted by (Wang et al., 2024) examining whether weekly PEG-IFN- α -2b doses of 180 µg could be safely given to patients with decompensated cirrhosis. However, the levels of HBsAg dropped markedly but either treatment withdrawal because of side effects from the therapy or patients developing resistance due to the treatment was unfortunately also observed. One or two attempts were made to study the subject of a combination of PEG-IFN with other antiviral drugs. In the (Yang et al., 2022) study, histological

evaluation of the liver and reverses of fibrosis in cirrhosis were better with the combined treatment. Still, there was no statistical difference in HBsAg and HBeAg seroconversion. Likewise, in the same manner, (Zhou et al., 2019) studied the effectiveness of consolidation therapy with PEG-IFN after HBeAg seroconversion and found lower rates of viral relapse amongst those treated on uninterrupted NA therapy. All these results indicated that the role of adjunct was more potentially beneficial for these PEG-IFN manipulations. Nevertheless, those were the deemed helpful interventions and the drawbacks could be defined, such as unwanted side effects and infusion reactions.

5. Discussion

5.1 Effectiveness of PEG-IFN Add-on and Switch Therapy in CHB Treatment

All of the reviewed studies conclude that the potential benefit of PEG-IFN add on or switch therapy yields better treatment outcomes than non PEG-IFN options for chronic Hepatitis B (CHB) patients on long term nucleos (t)ide analog (NA) therapy. Although several randomised controlled trials and observational studies have shown that PEG-IFN combination therapy increases HBsAg decline and clearance rates versus NA monotherapy, early viral rise and immunologist flare frequently occurred within 12 weeks, reducing HBsAg decline rates. For example, (Farag et al., 2024) observed 10% of HBsAg clearance rate in PEG-IFN add on patients but no clearance in the NA monotherapy patients. Like that, (Wu et al., 2020) and (Lim et al., 2022) reported that the loss and seroconversion rates of HBsAg are significantly higher with PEG-IFN than with NA alone. The reason for this effectiveness lies in the immunomodulatory abilities in PEG-IFN that significantly augment the ability of the body to get rid of infected hepatocytes. But response depends on individuals — especially baseline HBsAg levels and early treatment response — and leads to success. Despite promising results, PEG-IFN therapy appears to select a group of patients for whom the outcome is highly variable and should, therefore, include criteria for patient selection to maximize efficacy (Wang et al., 2024).

5.2 Tolerability and Safety Considerations of PEG-IFN Therapy

While PEG-IFN is effective, it has troubling adverse effect rates, the effects of which may interfere with patient adherence and therapy success. Weight loss, skin rashes, flu-like symptoms, headache, depression, cytopenia, and fatigue have all been reported as common side effects in one or more of the studies. According to (Wang et al., 2024)), three patients discontinued PEG-IFN because of adverse events, but no virological breakthrough nor disease progression occurred. Like (Hu et al., 2022), they also identified that the rates for the HBeAg seroconversion were improved when PEG-IFN add on therapy was added to NA in monotherapy. However, the rates for side effects were also higher than NA monotherapy. In light of these findings, patient counseling and treatment monitoring are extremely important to deal with adverse events. Also, patients who had had previous NA therapy may tolerate PEG-IFN more than those new to the therapy (Yan et al., 2025). For that reason, it is critical to choose proper candidates depending on disease stage, prior treatment history, and risk of adverse events in order to minimize therapy related outcome.

5.3 Efficacy of PEG-IFN in Different CHB Patient Populations

Key efficacy of PEG-IFN therapy for chronic hepatitis B (CHB) depends on patient population. The main difference is between HBeAg positive and HBeAg negative patients. Treatment of HBeAg positive patients with PEG-IFN in combination with NA as compared to NA alone carries higher rates of HBeAg seroconversion. For example, (Chi et al., 2017) and (Hu et al., 2022) showed that the administration of PEG-IFN add on therapy has significant increases in HBeAg seroconversion

compared to NA monotherapy. However, the treatment success is variable and depends on the patient's age, HBV genotype, and baseline HBsAg levels. In HBeAg-negative patients, PEG-IFN therapy is also more effective in inducing HBsAg decline and clearance. (Farag et al., 2024) and (Wu et al., 2020) studies have shown that this add-on of PEG-IFN significantly increased the rate of HBsAg clearing compared to NA monotherapy. Additionally, people who have been treated before may react differently than those who have never been treated. However, (Tatsukawa et al., 2018) reports that similar HBsAg clearance rates are observed in interferon-experienced and naïve patients, and the final outcome was affected by baseline HBsAg, early treatment response. Patient stratification according to pre-treatment characteristics may lead to optimum PEG-IFN therapy and hence improved overall success rates in the management of CHB.

5.4 PEG-IFN Add-on and Switch Strategies Comparison

Comparing PEG-IFN add-on therapy with a switch strategy is an area of research of major importance in the treatment of CHB. The add on treatment is that NA therapy is continued and combined with PEG-IFN which helps to increase immune control and promote HBsAg clearance. Its widespread scrutiny has shown better results than NA monotherapy. (Rui et al., 2025) and (Yan et al., 2025) demonstrated that PEG-IFN therapy with add on therapy provides better rates of HBsAg loss and seroconversion. Since early response to PEG-IFN predicts overall treatment success in patients with low baseline HBsAg levels, this method is particularly useful. In comparison, the switch strategy includes stopping NA treatment and replacing it with PEG IFN. Such an approach is explored to decrease the long-term NA dependency. But, according to (Zhou et al., 2019), although this may only increase the risk of virological relapse if one switches from NA to PEG-IFN. For this reason, some patients will lose the HBsAg, while others will re-activate the disease, possibly making this strategy less advantageous in some patients (Tatsukawa et al., 2018). Hence, the decision about which strategy, the add-on or the switch strategy, is made based on patient characteristics as well as baseline virological markers and risk tolerance. Refining predictive markers for each approach becomes future research so it can be used to select patients and increase treatment outcomes.

5.5 Clinical Implications and Future Research Directions

This systematic review's findings hold important clinical implications in the management of CHB, particularly for patients who have achieved viral suppression with NA therapy and require further strategies aimed at functional cures. Based on the results of adding or switching PEG-IFN therapy, the implication is that such therapy should be taken into account for carefully selected patients, including those with low baseline HBsAg and positive early treatment response (Zhang et al., 2024). However, treatment duration, dosing, and patient selection criteria need to be standardized. Future research should concentrate on biomarkers predictive of response to PEG-IFN to provide more personalized management of CHB. Longer follow up studies are also needed to determine how durable PEG-IFN-induced loss of HBsAg and seroconversion is. Thus, other combination strategies including the use of PEG-IFN in combination with emerging antiviral or immune modulatory agents should also be explored to optimize treatment efficacy with minimal side effects (Tatsukawa et al., 2018). In general, PEG-IFN therapy is a reasonable strategy for bringing the CHB patient to a functional cure. However, further investigation is needed to refine its use in clinical practice.

6. Conclusion

It is concluded in this systematic review that PEG-IFN add-on and switch therapy has the potential to improve treatment outcomes for CHB patients who have been on long-term NA therapy. Numerous studies clearly show that PEG-IFN is superior to NA monotherapy with regards to HBsAg decline, clearance, and seroconversion rates and is a viable, functional cure path. However, careful patient selection is still important because patient characteristics can cause variable responses. The immunomodulatory effects of PEG-IFN help to explain its activity, but treatment side effects (based on the PEG itself as well as the immunomodulatory effects) limit adherence and tolerability. PEG-IFN could compensate for the clinical inefficacy of other IFN types due to side effects. The benefits of PEG-IFN need to be weighed against the risks, and a selection of candidates for PEG-IFN based on predictive biomarkers is required. In the future, we need to test to optimize the treatment regimen, identify the response predictors and study the long term outcomes. Overall, PEG-IFN still has a promising but complex role as a therapeutic that needs individual patient management in order to maximize benefits and avoid risks.

7. Limitations

However, this review has several limitations that need to be noted. With respect to the included studies' comparability and generalizability, the first is that they are heterogeneous regarding patient populations, treatment protocols, and follow-up durations. Some studies had small sample sizes for their studies, from which the statistical power could not detect significant differences in treatment outcomes. Observational studies, along with RCTs, rely on such biases, where real-world data may not always closely resemble the controlled clinical setting. The limitation of another study is the variation of baseline patient characteristics such as HBsAg and previous treatment, which can affect response and direct comparisons among studies.

Additionally, PEG-IFN therapy appears promising, but its long-term efficacy and durability have not been demonstrated. These findings need to be validated and refined using well-controlled trials on larger numbers of patients using standardized protocols in future research. While these limitations exist, the review offers some important insights into the possibility of using PEG-IFN in the management of CHB.

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